

MICROCOMPUTER CONTROLLED FILAMENT WINDER

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The filament winding industry is gaining reputation as an efficient and economic composite processing technique over years past, mainly due to recent innovations in fiber placement capabilities of filament winding machinery. More and more product design engineers are finding the filament winding machines of today tremendous aids in their composite development work using glass, carbon fiber and Kevlar. This paper will describe the overall fiber placement capabilities of a standard microcomputer controlled filament winding machine and it will demonstrate this capability by showing actual mandrels being wound. A full description of how the fiber placement program is generated using the microcomputer in both linear and non-linear winding modes is given. Most complex filament wound composites of today require a filament winding machine with crossfeed motion which can keep the fiber band, being delivered to the mandrel, equidistant from the mandrel regardless of mandrel complexity. The crossfeed motion will be discussed and demonstrated. Another machine that filament wound products are using more and more is that of the rotating delivery eye which keeps the fiber band flat on sophisticated mandrel surface changes. A discussion of the rotating eye feature will go into specific detail to show design engineers this new fiber placement motion.

INTRODUCTION

The intent of this paper is to stimulate new thinking toward the creative utilization of a microcomputer controlled filament winding machine. Complex wound products are demanding continuous fiber placement machinery for the years ahead and the concepts presented here are intended to meet the challenge.

The reinforced plastics industry is experiencing a great deal of growth in the aerospace and automotive sectors. Widespread attention is being given to the high strength-to-weight ratio end products, and filament winding is emerging as an excellent continuous fiber placement process. The range of possible end products wound on a microcomputer controlled filament winding machine is broadened by the unique capabilities of the machinery presented here.

MICROCOMPUTER CONTROLLED FILAMENT WINDING

Filament winding is a reinforced plastic process that employs a series of continuous resin impregnated fibers applied to a rotating mandrel in a predetermined geometrical relationship under controlled tension. In the past, machinery used to place continuous reinforcements onto the rotating mandrel was mechanical in design. The relationship between the rotating spindle shaft and the traversing carriage was changed to affect varying wind angles. Because the filament winding machines of the past were mechanical, longhand gear ratio calculations, actual machine gear set-up, and multi-angle laminates required a great amount of time. The microcomputer controlled filament winding machines of the present allow for an entirely new approach to filament winding, saving a great amount of time.

The microcomputer controlled filament winding machines are programmable in both linear and non-linear modes. That is, the relationship between spindle rotation and carriage traverse can be linear or non-linear functions if plotted. Fiber placement is greatly aided by the use of a programmable servo crossfeed and rotating fiber delivery payout eye. In Figure 1, multi-axis machine motion is shown. The spindle axis, which can rotate in a clockwise or counterclockwise direction, is the independent axis of motion. While the mandrel is rotating, a carriage would translate parallel to the spindle axis. For additional fiber placement capability, a crossfeed translation, normal to the centerline of the spindle is available as well as a rotation about the axis of crossfeed translation. These machine motions are available to the design engineer so precise fiber band placement can be accomplished.

In Photo 1 a typical microcomputer controlled filament winding machine is shown. The machine has an independent mandrel and carriage drive. The operator can control the machine at a pushbutton station mounted on the mandrel drive cabinet. The microcomputer control (see Photo 3) is also mounted on the mandrel drive cabinet for fiber placement programming. The carriage runs the length of the machine, and mounted on the carriage itself, is the entire programmable servo crossfeed and rotating delivery eye housing. The closed loop control system utilizes encoder feedback to tell the microcomputer where each axis of machine motion is with respect to the independent spindle axis. Throughout the winding, precise fiber patterns are maintained with a high degree of accuracy. The entire machine described here utilizes DC (direct current) electric motors.

The microcomputer controlled filament winding machine described above is considered a classical type. The classical type filament winding machine is hereby defined as a rotating fixed mandrel with a translating carriage.

Another version of the microcomputer controlled filament winding machine is the oscillating mandrel type. The sketch in Figure 2 shows the machine motions of an oscillating mandrel type machine. This version has a fixed fiber delivery ring depositing filaments from a 360 degree range. While the delivery ring remains stationary, the mandrel rotates and traverses through the ring. Variations of

this machinery allow the reinforced plastics industry to use true hybrid composite manufacturing techniques at high volume rates.

USING THE MACHINE AND THE MICROCOMPUTER FOR ACCURATE FIBER PATTERNS

Three winding configurations will be presented here to demonstrate programming technique, fiber placement capability and the two types of microcomputer controlled filament winding machines.

Conical Section Multi-Axis Filament Winding

For many product applications, conical sections are of interest. The demonstration presented used a wooden mandrel with a 25.4 mm (1.0 in.) diameter at the small end, 266.7 mm (10.5 in.) diameter at the large end of the cone and the overall length was 457.2 mm (18 in.). The shape was a straight taper. In actual winding applications, this shape could be a rocket exit cone, or it could be expanded and re-shaped into an automotive bell housing.

This fiber placement requirement would be a non-linear winding. After a design decision has been made, a fiber path would be determined. The design engineer could then plot one fiber circuit onto the conical mandrel mounted in the machine.

One fiber circuit would be defined as one complete cycle of carriage motion. With the use of a non-linear programming box, the machine operator would have complete control of the carriage, crossfeed and rotating delivery eye for precise fiber placement. The first action the operator would take to program the non-linear fiber path would be to make the microcomputer aware of the recording to be made. The operator would address the keyboard in Photo 3 and would key CN for carriage non-linear. The computer would then ask for the number of circuits the operator wishes to have the fiber path repeated, and it also requests the operator to input an accuracy factor for the recording. The computer also finishes the brief sequence prior to winding by asking the operator if the mandrel should rotate clockwise or counterclockwise. The operator holds a non-linear programming box (hereafter defined as joystick, see Figure 3) and uses the pushbutton station to begin to rotate the mandrel very slowly. After the operator has a comfortable mandrel rotation underway, the carriage is activated by depressing the carriage axis pushbutton on the pushbutton station. With the fiber band attached to the rotating cone shape mandrel, the operator then varies the carriage velocity, with respect to constant mandrel rotation, to deposit the fiber band precisely onto the plotted fiber path. As the velocity of the carriage changes, the microcomputer, with its pre-programmed accuracy factor, records the position of the encoder mounted on the carriage drive motor. In this manner any fiber pattern can be programmed for advanced composite design.

After the recording has been made for one fiber circuit, the computer will display a "enter switch no." command on the cathode ray tube (CRT). The operator then assigns an identification number from 1 to 99 to lock this pre-recorded fiber path into the on-board memory. This program could be modified, using various commands, for larger bandwidths, point to point smoothing, or mandrel speed variations.

To run the non-linear program, the operator would first dial in the proper set-up select switches above the CRT (see Photo 3) corresponding to the identifying set-up number. The operator then would key a reset pushbutton, and then a run pushbutton. At this point the winding would begin.

The joystick programming technique has a distinct advantage of quick fiber placement with relatively simple input to the microcomputer. However, where highly critical fiber placement is required, such as aerospace applications, the joystick method only allows accuracies achieved with the skills of the machine operator. To aid these special cases, where continuous fiber paths are critical, a design engineer could interface a point to point predetermined fiber path with the microcomputer presented. This would then eliminate the joystick programming process,

and the non-linear carriage motions would be directly loaded into computer memory from another remote intelligent source.

The conical section shown in Photo 2 has a bandwidth that actually becomes wider as the fiber path approaches the largest end of the cone. By programming the rotating fiber payout eye to direct the fiber band, the operator could actually vary the fiber bandwidth. The programming method to actually widen the fiber band would make use of the previously described joystick method. The rotating fiber payout axis has 3.67 radians (210 degrees) of rotational deflection about the crossfeed translation axis.

In a non-linear mode of operation, the classical microcomputer controlled filament winding machine can wind very complex geometries. The crossfeed and rotating fiber payout eye can be designed to mount onto the floor mounted carriage bed, or the same motion may mount on an overhead carriage as shown partially in Photo 2. A variation of the overhead crossfeed and rotating fiber payout eye is shown in an entire machine configuration in Photo 4.

Complex Pipe Shapes

Not all filament winding applications require sophisticated multi-axis machine motion. Pipe shapes, considered to be the basics in filament winding, are wound with microcomputer controlled machine motion as well. For the purpose of demonstration, a pipe 762 mm (30 in.) in diameter, 6.10 mm (20 ft.) in length will be discussed. It will be assumed that the pipe will be comprised of two layers of surface mat, two layers of 54.75 degree helix, and a finish layer of circumferential. At the end of the winding it is also assumed that a dwell of one fiber band is required 101.6 mm (4 in.) in from one end of the pipe. A bandwidth of 165.1 mm (6.5 in.) is required during the winding.

The microcomputer controlled filament winding machine required for this pipe winding would be a single axis unit, that is, a mandrel drive and a translating carriage controlled by a microcomputer. The machine motion for the winding is all linear motion which can be programmed on the keyboard shown in Photo 3. The surface mat could be applied with an auxiliary function control available to the operator. A roll of surface mat mounted on a delivery head, also fixed to the carriage, could be commanded to drop down on the rotating mandrel at a precise time in the early stages of the winding. Again, using auxiliary function control (110 volt on-off signals available to the programmer anytime during a winding sequence) the microcomputer could activate a resin spray gun mounted on the carriage. The operator could program the resin impregnation gun to energize and de-energize as needed during the application of the surface mat. To program the 54.75 helix, circumferential, and dwell fiber patterns, the operator would address the keyboard directly. The two letter identifier command for the helix would be "PE". The operator, upon keying "PE", would see all the winding parameters ready for programming on the CRT display. The starting position of the carriage would be programmed as the "H" (mm) position of "home" position. This would precisely position the carriage at the proper starting position, pipe after pipe. An imaginary carriage drive sprocket radius "R" (mm) would be programmed to govern carriage dwell at the turnarounds of the pipe. The operator would then program the diameter "D" (mm) of the mandrel, in this case 762 mm (30 in.). This could also be the mean diameter of the pipe is so desired. The circuits per patterns "C" could also be loaded into the microcomputer. Because it is assuming that two layers of 54.75 degree helix will be needed, the programmer can command the microcomputer to wind two layers by defining "N", number of layers, equal to two. The mandrel drive gear ratio "M" and the desired turnaround "T" in degrees of mandrel rotation must be programmed. By varying the turnaround input, the operator can precisely control the amount of end waste of the finished pipe. This pipe example requires a winding length "L" (mm) of 6096.0 mm (240 in.). The winding angle (measured from the longitudinal centerline of the mandrel) "A" (degrees) is input as 54.75. The bandwidth "W" (mm) would also be keyed into the microcomputer, and for this example, 165.1 mm (6.5 in.) would be a required bandwidth. The true bandwidth is always measured

on an axis normal to the edge of the fiber band. The operator has the option of programming a leading or lagging bandwidth for the pipe program.

After all of the 54.75 helix pipe program parameters are loaded into the microcomputer, the operator keys "G" for go, and the microcomputer takes all of the input data, and generates a true winding program. A value for the circuits per layer "Z", the dwell in degrees of mandrel rotation, the actual turnaround in degrees of mandrel rotation, and "C" circuits per pattern will be displayed. A very important updated "W", or true bandwidth, will also appear on the CRT display. It is the operators responsibility to make certain the band of fibers coming from the resin bath agrees with the actual "W". The operator then would key another two letter identifier sequence "AS", for assign, to load the previously programmed helix into a set-up select switch position as previously described.

The circumferential winding program would be programmed by directing the computer to open the internal circumferential "CR" program. In the "CR" program, the operator need to program "H", "M", "W", "N" and "L" to generate a valid winding program. The microcomputer will control the carriage such that for each revolution of the mandrel, the carriage advance equals one bandwidth "W". The operator would also use the "S" subroutine to hold this circumferential winding program in a set-up select switch position for later recall.

Proper programming techniques must be followed to insure proper fiber placement. A dwell program is also programmed by keying in "DW". On the CRT the dwell program can be generated. The operator must program a location of the carriage during the dwell, in this case the "H" position from the 54.75 degree helix program plus 101.6 mm (4 in.). The operator must also define the number of mandrel revolutions required during the dwell, and "M", mandrel ratio. This dwell program also would be assigned to its own set-up select switch position.

To load this entire pipe winding sequence into the microcomputer for permanent recall during production, a very simple program is called up by still another two letter command. The operator keys the command "CM". The CRT then asks for a set-up select switch to be the input as the first level of machine operation. For this demonstration it is assumed that the surface mat sequence is stored in set-up select switch 10, the 54.75 degree helix is loaded in switch 11, the circumferential is in switch 12 and the dwell is loaded in switch 13. All of these base levels of machine motion can be programmed to run the entire filament wound pipe in proper sequence without gear changes or set-up procedures. One entire set-up select switch could be designated as the 30 inch diameter by 20 foot random pipe section. The machine operator would dial in the proper set-up select switch to run the pipe, and the same pushbutton sequence would be performed to run the winding program, as previously described in the conical section winding.

Some of the major advantages of the microcomputer control for pipe winding machine motion are; increased program sequencing, unlimited fiber angle selections, varying mandrel speeds programmed for each layer, mitre cut marking capability, automatic set-up select for changing product lines from the same machine and uniformity of end products.

Oscillating Mandrel Type Machine for Hybrid Composites

The hybrid composites are going to play a very important role in the future of the reinforced plastics industry. Interest in carbon fiber/fiberglass composites as well as Kevlar combinations show the need for high volume process machinery to process continuous fibers at high speeds. The oscillating mandrel type (OMT) microcomputer controlled filament winding machine is a high production filament winding machine designed for the production of tubular products up to 508.0 mm (20 in.) in diameter. It is capable of the consecutive dispensing of two types of resin impregnated continuous strand reinforcement in layers at pre-programmed winding angles. The machine utilizes 360 degree fiber placement in its fiber delivery systems. This type of fiber delivery reduces end waste, improves product physicals, improves product appearance and achieves higher production rates.

The machine is state of the art. It is equipped with a computerized control system and has a fixed position reinforcement storage and delivery system combined with a moving tooling drive system. In this design the reinforcement, impregnation and delivery system remains stationary while the mandrel is both rotated and longitudinally translated past the delivery system. The machine is equipped with automatic devices for transferring from one reinforcement type to a second, as well as starting and stopping the winding of either reinforcement type. The machine is also designed for automatic mandrel loading and unloading so that it can be fully integrated as a station in a multi-step manufacturing system.

The advent of computer controlled filament winding equipment such as the OMT gives rise to a number of distinct advantages over conventional equipment. These include the ability to fully automate the filament winding process, fully integrate filament winding as a part of other highly automated manufacturing processes, program an almost infinite variety of winding configurations, produce more highly complex composite structures, to produce product of more consistent quality due to the capability of the equipment to automatically control more areas of the manufacturing process, and produce product at higher production rates due to the greater degree of machine control of the process.

FILAMENT WINDING RISING TO THE CHALLENGE

The reinforced plastics industry is truly going to play an important role in the quest for new light weight structures to save energy and to improve product performance. Never before has the need for continuous fiber end products been so great. The advent of the the family of microcomputer controlled filament winding machines presented here provides the design engineer with a new improved fiber placement tool. Both linear and non-linear filament winding patterns are programmed easily and quickly to wind Kevlar, carbon fiber or fiberglass around virtually any shape. The filament winding industry will be a very important group rising to the challenge in the months and years ahead. The world may see an entire jumbo jet fuselage section wound by 1990, and automotive is already deeply involved in filament winding using the microcomputer control presented here. The world of microcomputers and the world of filament winding have just joined to form a very useful reinforced plastics process.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Oscillating Mandrel Machine Motion

Figure 3
Non-Linear Programming Box

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7